

The Mythical “True Counter-Tenor” Rides Again

Being a Critical Examination of *The Supernatural Voice: A History of High Male Singing* by Simon Ravens (Boydell Press, 2014)

The old “true counter-tenor” (as opposed to mere male alto/falsettist) canard is brought out and given a worrying in this portentously laboured “revisionist history”. Penned in an irksome modern style, replete with up to the minute jargon such as “fully-modal”, and purportedly of interest to “readers of all sorts”. Author Simon Ravens sets out to debunk the belief that the historical counter-tenor used a developed falsetto, and was in fact a high light tenor. He claims that the falsettist counter-tenor is an invention of the twentieth century. And (it may be thought) rather disingenuously entitles the introduction to his book: *A Declaration of Disinterest*. To digress a little: As the great Sidney Toler intoned in *Charlie Chan in the Secret Service* (Monogram Pictures, 1944): “When alibi pushed at me, always suspect motive in woodpile.”

To Set the Scene

Composer Michael Tippett first heard Canterbury Cathedral alto, Alfred Deller, sing Henry Purcell’s *Music for a While* in 1944. Tippett later wrote that: “for me, in that moment the centuries rolled back.” Deller’s subsequent success paved the way for the modern renaissance of the counter-tenor voice. And since then debate has raged about the history, description, and true nature of the voice; most of which was summed up—sensibly—by Dr. Peter Giles in his several books upon the subject.

Deller, as a solo artist, and as a member of his own consort, made a big impact in the revival of interest in the music of Henry Purcell—among others. Benjamin Britten created the part of Oberon in his opera *A Midsummer Night’s Dream* specifically for Deller. Deller created the role at the Aldeburgh Festival in 1960 but was passed over for the Covent Garden production in favour of the American counter-tenor Russell Oberlin. Writing of the success of James Bowman, who succeeded Deller and Oberlin in the role, Ravens states:

Bowman credits his operatic success with his tendency to ‘show off’ and on his ability ‘to make a lot of noise.’ *Many a true word* [my italics—you can almost hear Ravens saying “Nudge nudge, wink wink!”] Deller had been dropped [he wasn’t dropped, he was never engaged] from the Covent Garden production of *A Midsummer Night’s Dream* because his acting was considered too stilted, and his voice too small [Ravens, p. 209].

It’s true that Deller was not regarded as a good actor, but the assertion that he was passed over because his voice was too small is not justified by any documented reference.

The American counter-tenor, Russell Oberlin, came to prominence with Noah Greenberg’s New York Pro Musica Antiqua in the early 1950s. In 1962 he took part in a Camera Three television broadcast in which he was interviewed briefly and mimed selections from recordings he’d made for experience anonymes and Deutsche Grammophon. In this broadcast Oberlin states that he sings in his “natural high tenor” voice, does not use falsetto, and makes a clear distinction between “true counter-tenor” and male alto/falsettist. Ravens: “In regarding the counter-tenor as a modal voice Oberlin was only following an American usage.” Well, we shall see. The American organist, choirmaster, and counter-tenor himself, George Edward Stubbs, in his: *The Adult Male Alto or Counter-Tenor Voice* (New York, 1908) states: “There are two varieties of the counter-tenor voice. First, there is a species of high, light tenor...Second, there is the so-called ‘falsetto alto,’ in which

the falsetto register is distinctly separated from the chest register.”ⁱ So much for Ravens’s assertion that: “in American usage the term counter-tenor had *always* [my italics] referred to a high modal voice,” The liner notes for two of Russell Oberlin’s earliest recordings, published on LP in 1953 and 1955 (and reissued on CD in 2006), give no indication that Oberlin—at that time—endorsed any distinction between “true counter-tenor” and male alto/falsettist: “The practice of an alto part being sung by a male voice was at one time as commonplace as it is now novel...In these days of conscientious and faithful performance of old music it should be mentioned that until around 1750 a vocal part scored for alto was properly sung by a male voice.”ⁱⁱ In 1960 Oberlin’s album of Handel arias recorded for Deutsche Grammophon was published. The liner notes mention both Deller and Oberlin as outstanding modern day counter-tenors, but again there is no indication of any distinction between “true counter-tenor” and male alto/falsettist. It is clear that by the time of the 1962 Camera Three broadcast Oberlin was feeling sufficiently emboldened to put forward this groundless distinction. The Camera Three broadcast was issued on DVD by VAI (Video Artists International). The disc includes an interview recorded with Mr. Oberlin in 2004, in which, interestingly, he quietly tries to back-peddle from his 1962 stance. He admits that, “most, if not all the counter-tenors singing today use their falsetto voices” and rather meekly refers to his own “naturally high tenor voice” as, “just a difference.”ⁱⁱⁱ Oberlin began to experience vocal difficulties in 1962/63; apparently caused by his coaxing his voice into stratospheric regions to which it probably should not have aspired. He later admitted as much (see review of the CD: *Russell Oberlin: Music of John Blow and Henry Purcell*, by Fanfare magazine contributor Lynn Rene Bayley).^{iv} The subsequent deterioration of his voice occasioned his retirement from public performance in 1964 at the age of thirty-six. Later, happily, he found a new metier in teaching.

The Kernel of the Matter

Being the author of this short piece it occurs to me that I’m like to be called in question in view of its brevity. It has not been my object in writing this to subject the entire matter of Ravens’s tome to critical scrutiny. The few careless errors of fact to which I have already drawn attention should suffice to enable the perceptive reader to draw his/her own conclusion as to how much reliance can be placed on the level of scholarship demonstrated in the work. It seems to me that there are two types of scholarship. First, there is the scholar who takes great care to assemble his facts, check them, and present them fairly and objectively; taking pains to make it perfectly clear that any personal opinions propounded are just that. Second, there is that type of scholar who “knows” he’s right, and expects everyone else to know it too. When such a scholar asserts mere opinion—opinion that demonstrates a clear personal bias—as though it were established fact, that’s not scholarship—it’s propaganda. And so to the kernel of the matter: The main premise of Mr. Ravens’s book—upon which the entire edifice must stand or fall—his solution to the supposed mystery of why the mythical “true counter-tenor” became extinct to be replaced—with ever increasing velocity—in the twentieth century by the male alto/falsettist. Ravens (in his jargon fond style):

The fundamentally modal countertenor, known in England and Europe until the mid-nineteenth century, and subsequently in America, now falls virtually mute. How can we explain this silence. The theme of rising height has been a leitmotif of this history, and here it must be sounded again. Although height has risen steadily throughout modern history, and the pitch of modal voices has subsequently dropped, until the latter half of the twentieth century this trend was very slow. Since the Second World War, nutrition in the western world has resulted in the trend rapidly accelerating. As a result, even fully modal tenors are becoming thinner on the ground [!]. Into the territory vacated by high modal voices, the falsettists have marched in ever increasing numbers

[Ravens, p. 210].

Ahem. Well dear reader, if you've stayed with me thus far I reckon you can guess where Mr. Ravens is going. It boils down to this—in the “olden days” people were the next-best thing to midgets, so they had higher pitched voices!

Dead Men Tell

In August 1996 a mass burial pit was discovered near Towton in Yorkshire. The site—in 1461—of a battle; reputedly the bloodiest battle of the Wars of the Roses. The mostly complete remains of forty-three individuals, who died in the battle, were recovered and examined by a team of osteoarchaeologists and archaeologists from the University of Bradford. The findings were reported in an unattributed article published in *The Economist*:

It is the only mass grave of medieval battle victims to have been found in England. The men whose skeletons were unearthed at Towton were a diverse lot. Their ages at time of death ranged widely . . . the youngest occupants of the mass grave were around 17 years old; the oldest . . . around 50. Their stature varies greatly too. The men's height ranges from 1.5-1.8 metres (just under five feet to just under six feet), with the older men, almost certainly experienced soldiers being tallest. This physical diversity is unsurprising, given the disparate types of men who took the battlefield that day. Yet as a group the Towton men are a reminder that images of the medieval man as a homunculus with rotten teeth are well wide of the mark. The average medieval man stood 1.71 metres tall – just four centimetres shorter than a modern Englishman. ‘It is only in the Victorian era that people started to get very stunted,’ says Mr Knusel [Christopher Knusel, one of the original archaeologists on site]. Their health was generally good. Dietary isotopes from their knee-bones show that they ate pretty healthily. Sugar was not widely available at that time, so their teeth were strong too.^v

What? No Munchkins? That's a pity. The image of legions of Jimmy Clitheroe like choristers helping medieval, renaissance, and barock choirs to soar in fully-modal, “true counter-tenor” stratospheric fashion is priceless!

Happy days. Tom Henshaw

i George Edward Stubbs, *The Adult Male Alto or Counter-Tenor Voice* (New York: The H.W. Gray Co., 1908), p.14, accessed 7 May, 2016.

ii Max Serbin, and Anon., liner notes to *Russell Oberlin: Music of John Blow and Henry Purcell*, VAIA 1258, CD, 2006.

iii *Russell Oberlin: America's Legendary Countertenor*, VAI 4305, DVD, 2004.

iv Lynn Rene Bayley, *Purcell, Blow: Songs/Russell Oberlin, Et Al*, CD review, ArkivMusic, accessed 7 May, 2016.

v Anon., *Nasty, brutish and not that short*, *The Economist*, December 16, 2010, accessed 7 May, 2016.

i
ii
iii
iv
v